

THE ROLE OF IMMUNOLOGICAL MARKERS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF STABLE ANGINA IN ELDERLY WOMEN WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Annotation

The study analyzed clinical and immunological features of the course of stable angina pectoris in 208 elderly women (60-74 years, mean age 66.0 ± 6.0 years) suffering from grade II-III arterial hypertension. Depending on the functional class (FC) of stable angina, patients were distributed as follows: FC-1- 58 (32.6%), FC-2 — 62 (34.8%), FC-3 — 58 (32.6%). The control group consisted of 30 women with progressive angina pectoris. Biochemical, cytokine (IL-6, TNF- α) and immunological parameters were evaluated. A relationship was established between the severity of the disease and the level of inflammatory markers, which made it possible to determine prognostic criteria for differential diagnosis of stable angina in elderly women with hypertension.

Keywords

Ischemic heart disease, stable angina, arterial hypertension, elderly women, cytokines, immune status, prognosis.

Relevance

Stable angina in combination with arterial hypertension in elderly women is an urgent problem of modern cardiology. In this age group, the frequency of arterial hypertension reaches 65-70%, and angina symptoms are detected in more than 30% of patients. Features of the immune status in elderly women with CHD and concomitant hypertension are still insufficiently studied. Chronic inflammation, cytokine imbalance, and impaired immunoregulation are known to play a key role in the progression of coronary heart disease. However, the diagnostic criteria that reflect the severity of these changes are still not fully defined. In this regard, it is important to study clinical and immunological indicators that allow us to assess the severity of the disease, predict the development of complications and optimize therapy. This study is aimed at solving this problem, which makes it possible to increase the efficiency of managing this category of patients.

Research objective

Comprehensive clinical and immunological characteristics of stable angina pectoris in elderly women with arterial hypertension for the development of prognostic criteria for the severity of the disease.

Materials and methods

The study included 208 women with IHD and grade II–III arterial hypertension aged 60–74 years (mean age 66.0 ± 6.0 years). The main group consisted of patients with stable angina: FC-1–58 (32.6%), FC-2 — 62 (34.8%), FC-3 — 58 (32.6%). The comparison group included 30 patients with progressive angina pectoris. Clinical data, general blood count, biochemical profile, levels of proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α), circulating immune complexes, and CD4+ and CD8+ lymphocyte counts were studied. Statistical data processing was carried out using correlation analysis methods.

Results

The data obtained indicate an increase in inflammatory and immune disorders with an increase in the functional class of angina pectoris. Elevated concentrations of IL-6 (15.2 ± 1.4 pg/ml) and TNF- α (19.7 ± 1.6 pg/ml) were recorded in patients with FC-3, which is higher than in the FC-1 group (8.6 ± 0.9 pg/ml and 11.2 ± 1.3 pg/ml, respectively; $p < 0.01$). CEC reached 123.4 ± 5.2 U/ml in FC-3 versus 84.6 ± 4.3 U/ml in FC-1 ($p < 0.05$). The CD4+/CD8+ index increased to 2.8 ± 0.2 in severe cases ($p < 0.05$). Significant correlations were found between cytokine levels and clinical parameters ($r = 0.62-0.68$; $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion

In elderly women with a combination of stable angina pectoris and grade II–III arterial hypertension, significant immune changes were detected: an increase in IL-6, TNF- α , and CIC levels, as well as a violation of the CD4+/CD8+ lymphocyte ratio. These indicators significantly correlate with the severity of angina, reflected by the functional class of the disease. The clinical and immunological indicators developed on the basis of the obtained data allow not only to clarify the severity of the pathological process, but also to predict the risk of CHD progression in this category of patients. The use of these criteria in clinical practice can contribute to a personalized approach to patient management and improve the effectiveness of therapy.

Literature:

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